

Argüello Gutiérrez, C., Carretero-Dios, H., Willis, G. B., & Moya, M. (2018). Joking about ourselves: Effects of disparaging humor on ingroup stereotyping. *Group Processes & Intergroup Relations*, 21(4), 568-583. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1368430216674339>

Joking about ourselves: Effects of disparaging humor on ingroup stereotyping

Catalina Argüello Gutiérrez,¹ Hugo Carretero-Dios,¹ Guillermo B. Willis,¹ and Miguel Moya¹

Abstract

In three studies, we examined whether ingroup disparaging humor leads to greater stereotyping of the ingroup. First, in Study 1, ($N = 101$) university students were exposed to (a) ingroup disparaging humor, (b) neutral humor, or (c) ingroup disparaging nonhumorous text. Participants exposed to disparaging humor reported more stereotypic evaluations than those in the neutral humor or disparaging text condition. Study 2 ($N = 167$) replicated these findings with humor conditions (disparaging vs. neutral) and showed that ingroup identification moderated the effects of the type of humor. Low identifiers exposed to ingroup disparaging humor (vs. those in the control condition) reported a greater frequency of stereotypic evaluations, whereas the manipulation did not affect high identifiers. Finally, Study 3 ($N = 153$) also manipulated the source of the jokes. As in Study 2, we found an interaction effect showing that high identifiers were not affected by the manipulation, whereas for low identifiers disparaging humor increased stereotyping and led to more negative emotions toward the ingroup. No significant effects were found for source of the jokes. We discuss findings in terms of how the traditional pattern of humor facilitating outgroup stereotyping also seems to apply to ingroup stereotyping.

Keywords

disparaging humor, identification, ingroup evaluation, social identity, stereotypes

Disparagement humor seems to allow people to express their negative attitudes. Research has shown that disparaging humor promotes a climate of tolerance for the expression of prejudice and discrimination (Ford & Ferguson, 2004). Exposure to this kind of humor may therefore increase tolerance of racist and ethnic discrimination (Ford, 1997; Ford, Boxer, Armstrong, & Edel, 2008; Ford, Woodzicka, Triplett, Kochersberger, & Holden, 2013), of sexist attitudes (Ford, Wentzel, & Lorion, 2001; Romero-Sánchez, Durán, Carretero-Dios, Megías, & Moya, 2010; Viki, Thomae, Cullen, & Fernandez, 2007), and facilitates a worse evaluation of minority and low-power social groups (Argüello, Willis, & Carretero-Dios, 2012; Maio, Olson, & Bush, 1997). Ford and Ferguson (2004) developed the prejudiced norm theory to explain the effects of disparaging humor, that is, communication intended as a direct and obvious attack on a characteristic of a person or specific group, promoting entertainment through denigration, humiliation, and contempt (Ferguson & Ford, 2008; Ford & Ferguson, 2004). Building on the justification– suppression model (Crandall & Eshleman, 2003) which argues that prejudices are not expressed directly, but are restricted by both internal (e.g., personal values, moral standards, or religious beliefs) and external forces (e.g., egalitarian standards and social norms), Ford and Ferguson (2004) stated that humor serves as a facilitator of prejudice, acting as a justification that legitimizes its expression by promoting the adoption of a mental state of nonseriousness during humor appreciation (Ford & Ferguson, 2004). In other words, exposure to disparagement humor changes external sources of self-regulation, creating a social setting that encourages the expression of existing prejudice against the targeted group (Ford, Richardson, & Petit, 2015).

However, little is known about how disparaging humor might encourage the expression of negative attitudes and stereotypes toward the ingroup. Although some research has examined perceived aversiveness and funniness of gender disparaging jokes (e.g., Abrams & Bippus, 2011; Thomae & Pina, 2015), none has yet established whether disparagement humor could influence how the ingroup is perceived. In this paper we aim to fill this gap by examining whether exposure to disparagement humor toward the ingroup leads to greater stereotyping and a worse ingroup evaluation.

Disparaging Humor and Ingroup Identification

Social identity theory posits a link between identity and group membership, as well as a tendency toward an ingroup bias (Tajfel & Turner, 1979). From this perspective, individuals would tend to reject jokes in which the ingroup (but not the out-group) is disparaged. For instance, Abrams and Bippus (2011) conducted a study presenting men and women jokes about their gender and the opposite gender. Results showed that women exhibited ingroup bias by rating jokes about their men funnier and more typical than jokes about their own gender. Similarly, Carretero-Dios, Pérez, and Buela-Casal (2010) showed that males are more amused with disparaging humor, as long as it is women those who are disparaged and not men.

Individuals might react differently to ingroup's disparagement humor as a function of their social identification (the degree to which individuals accept and follow group norms; McAuliffe, Jetten, Hornsey, & Hogg, 2003; Postmes, Spears, & Lea, 2000). Individuals who strongly identify with the ingroup will be more motivated to protect the group's image (Matera, Giannini, Blanco, & Smith, 2005), and to affirm their group selves (Spears et al., 2004).

Likewise, Coull, Yzerbyt, Castano, Paladino, and Leemans (2001) showed that higher identifiers devoted more cognitive resources to maintain a positive image of the ingroup by trying to solve an inconsistency of information that threatened group image. Conversely, when social identity is threatened, low identifiers may try to distance themselves from the group (Ellemers, Wilke, & van Knippenberg, 1993).

Building on these notions, the less one identifies with a social category, the more amused one should be at humor disparaging that social category (McGraw & Warren, 2010). Thus, for low identifiers, who tend to focus more on protecting self rather than group identity (Spears et al., 2004) and who are less willing to invest cognitive resources in solving inconsistent information about the ingroup (Coull et al., 2001), ingroup's disparagement humor might have similar consequences than outgroup's disparagement humor has; that is, it creates a social setting that encourages the expression of existing stereotypes and prejudice against the ingroup (Ford et al., 2015). However, high identifiers, due to their willingness to protect the ingroup's image (Matera et al., 2005), will not be influenced by disparagement humor. Therefore, whereas high identifiers will analyze the information about the ingroup more critically, independently of how it is presented (in a humorous or nonhumorous way), low identifiers will tend to accept negative information about it when such information is presented in a way that promotes a nonseriousness mindset (when it is presented as a joke). These predictions are congruent with past studies: female participants were more amused by sexist humor the less they identified with women as a social category (Kochersberger, Ford, Woodzicka, Romero-Sanchez, & Carretero-Dios, 2014), while highly identified women frowned more when listening to sexist jokes, suggesting that they were experiencing negative affect (LaFrance & Woodzicka, 1998).

The Present Research

Since most studies that have analyzed the effects of disparagement humor toward the ingroup have used women as the ingroup (Abrams & Bippus, 2011; Ford, 2000; Kochersberger et al., 2014), we decided to expand the study of this phenomenon using a different ingroup: university students. Given that part of university students' stereotype in Spain includes traits such as lazy, party-oriented, and disinterested (Puertas, 2003), we explored whether humor in which university students are disparaged would lead to greater ingroup stereotyping, worse ingroup evaluation, and in which conditions these effects might be stronger. In Study 1, we analyzed the impact of disparaging humor (compared with neutral humor and a disparagement nonhumorous text control condition) on stereotyping and average evaluation of the ingroup. We expected that individuals exposed to disparaging humor will report greater stereotyping and more negative average evaluation of the ingroup, compared with those in the neutral humor or disparaging text conditions.

In Studies 2 and 3, we aimed to replicate the results of Study 1 and tested our main prediction: that group identification would moderate the effect of disparaging humor. We expect that for low identifiers exposed to disparaging humor, stereotyping will be higher than for low identifiers exposed to neutral humor, whereas for high identifiers, no effects of humor type will be observed.

In Study 3 we also examined if the source of the joke can influence the effects of humor on the ingroup, that is, whether jokes told by a member of the ingroup have the same effects than jokes told by a member of the outgroup (see Ford, 2000).

Pilot Study

To have adequate stimuli for our research, the selection of humorous material came from a pilot study involving 102 university students (55 female, 47 male) aged between 18 and 32 ($M = 22.19$, $SD = 3.09$). Participants evaluated 32 jokes selected by the authors under the criterion that they presented disparaging content towards university students (17 jokes) or neutral humor (16 jokes). In the disparaging humor condition, all the jokes presented at least one negative stereotype of the group; namely they portrayed university students as: (a) party-oriented, revelers, or frequent alcohol drinkers, or (b) lazy, having a devil-may-care attitude, or disinterested. One example of these jokes is: "What's the last thing a university student does before taking an exam? Take something for the hangover!"¹

Neutral jokes were defined as those that made no reference to specific attributes of an individual or group (see Carretero-Dios et al., 2010). For example: A waiter to the client: "We have a menu of nine euro and a menu of six euro"; Client: "And what's the difference?"; Waiter: "Three euro." A complete list of the jokes used can be seen in Appendix A in the online supplementary materials. The items were rated on a two unipolar 5-point scales for funniness (0 = *not funny at all*, 4 = *very funny*) and aversiveness (0 = *not aversive at all*, 4 = *very aversive*).

To select the material, we applied principal components factor analysis and subsequent varimax rotation of funniness responses elicited by the jokes ($KMO = 0.83$; Bartlett's sphericity test: $\chi^2 = 332.09$, $df = 45$, $p < .001$). Two clearly differentiated factors emerged: Factor 1 corresponded to disparagement humor (eigenvalue of 2.41) and Factor 2 represented neutral humor (eigenvalue of 2.18). These factors explained 55.64% of total variance, while factor loadings ranged from 0.49 to 0.80 for the disparagement humor factor, and from 0.53 to 0.87 for the neutral humor factor. Both factors included items with different formats (jokes and cartoons) and extensions, discarding a factorial solution due to formal, rather than conceptual aspects. Five jokes were selected from each humor type, making sure there were no statistically significant differences between the jokes' funniness scores, $M_{\text{disparagement humor}} = 1.36$, $SD = 0.90$; $M_{\text{neutral humor}} = 1.46$, $SD = 0.97$; $t(101) = -1.15$, $p = .251$. As in other studies (Romero-Sánchez et al., 2010; Weinstein, Hodgins, & Ostvik-White, 2011), statistically significant differences were found between the two factors' aversiveness scores, $M_{\text{disparagement humor}} = 1.12$, $SD = 1.15$; $M_{\text{neutral humor}} = 0.50$, $SD = 0.85$; $t(99) = 6.26$, $p < .001$. No significant differences by sex or age were found in funniness or aversiveness scores. Scores on the items selected to comprise the disparagement humor factor yielded a Cronbach's alpha of .73, neutral humor factor an alpha of .80.

The mean funniness scores were 1.36 ($SD = 0.90$) for disparaging jokes, and 1.46 ($SD = 0.97$) for neutral jokes, similar to those found in other humor studies using disparaging humor (Kochersberger et al., 2014; Romero-Sánchez et al., 2010).

Study 1

As pointed out by the existing literature, the effects of disparagement humor are not due as much to prejudiced content as to their humorous format, given that such effects cannot be explained by simple priming (Ford et al., 2001). As such, Study 1 explored the differential effects of humor exposure on an ingroup's evaluation and stereotyping. The conditions we used were neutral humor, disparaging humor, and disparaging text, enabling the analysis of differences according to humor type as well as the ability to contrast them with nonhumorous disparaging material. We investigated whether participants were more willing to stereotype their ingroup and also whether they would evaluate it more negatively when information about the ingroup came from disparaging humor. We expected that exposure to ingroup-targeted disparaging humor would promote a more stereotypic vision of the ingroup than neutral humor or a disparaging text (Hypothesis 1a). We also expected that in the condition of exposure

to ingroup-targeted disparaging humor, the average evaluation of the ingroup would be worse than in the other two experimental conditions (Hypothesis 1b).

Method

Participants and design. One hundred and one undergraduate students from the University of Granada (49 male and 52 female) participated in this study, aged between 18 and 33 ($M = 21.06$, $SD = 3.15$). Participation was voluntary. In this study, participants were randomly assigned to one of the three experimental conditions: disparaging humor, neutral humor, and disparaging text. Group stereotyping and evaluation were measured as dependent variables.

Materials and measures. In each of the humor conditions, five jokes from the pilot study were presented. Meanwhile, in the disparaging information condition, a text with newspaper format was presented. This text portrayed students with the same stereotypic content as the disparaging jokes. For each joke and text, the degree of funniness and aversiveness was obtained using the same procedure as in the pilot study. The items were rated on two unipolar 5-point scales for “funniness” and “aversiveness.”

We followed a similar procedure to that used in other humor studies (Ford et al., 2001) to gain more control on the humorous stimuli and avoid simple priming effects. Thus, the content of disparaging jokes was converted into a nonhumorous disparaging text to communicate the stereotypes implied in the jokes. For instance, one disparaging joke was:

The three main reasons for a university student to go to the library:

1. To chat people up.
2. To chat people up.
3. To chat people up.

In the nonhumorous disparaging text condition, the joke was converted into a paragraph of text (see Appendix B in the online supplementary materials.): “Instead of going to consult the extensive literature resources, the norm is to go to the library as if it were a social club, where social networking or even chatting people up is the main objective.”

Stereotyping and average evaluation. These two variables were obtained from an open-ended measure based on the work of Esses and Zanna (1995) and used in a previous study on humor (Argüello et al., 2012). This measure has two steps that correspond to our two dependent variables. In the first step, participants were asked to write down four characteristics they considered typical of university students. Later on, and for analysis purposes, from the total written characteristics, we counted those that related specifically to the stereotypes presented in the disparaging jokes and text. This was the stereotyping measure and it ranged from 0 to 4, corresponding to the number of stereotypes written by each participant (from none to four). Specifically, the stereotypes taken in consideration were the same presented in the experiment (in the disparaging humor and text conditions). To establish what characteristics were and were not stereotypes, external observers classified each attribute as related to the stereotype or not. Using the same open-ended measure described before, the second step was to ask participants to return to those characteristics they had written and assess each one on a scale from -3 (*extremely negative*) to $+3$ (*extremely positive*). Afterwards, we created a mean value corresponding to the average evaluation of the characteristics for each participant. This was our second dependent variable: average evaluation, which ranged from -3 to $+3$.

Other variables. Age, gender, and career were registered. Also, for the disparaging humor and disparaging text conditions, we asked for the perceived degree of denigration and the degree in which participants perceived that the characteristics portrayed in the stimuli corresponded to real features of university students. These statements were rated on a 5-point scale (0 = *not at all*, 4 = *completely*).

Procedure. Booklets containing survey material were administered to participants in study rooms of the University of Granada libraries by the first author; students were asked to fill out the booklets. The booklets were allegedly an opinion survey about different topics published on the university's online newsletter. We randomly distributed booklets corresponding to the three experimental conditions (disparagement humor vs. neutral humor vs. disparaging text) to those who voluntarily agreed to participate in the study. The average time to fill out the booklet was 10 minutes. Finally, we thanked participants for their time and they received a brief description of the research.

Results

Preliminary analysis. As expected, disparaging ($M = 1.41$, $SD = 1.02$) and neutral jokes ($M = 1.39$, $SD = 0.82$) were perceived as equally funny, $t(64) = 0.105$, $p = .916$. However, disparaging jokes were significantly more aversive ($M = 1.55$, $SD = 1.56$) than neutral jokes were ($M = 0.74$, $SD = 1.01$), $t(67) = 2.54$, $p = .014$. Also, no differences were found in aversiveness for disparaging text ($M = 1.79$, $SD = 1.24$) and disparaging humor ($M = 1.55$, $SD = 1.55$), $t(65) = 0.68$, $p = .497$. Participants perceived that the nonhumorous text was more denigrating to students than disparaging humor, $M = 6.29$, $SD = 2.14$; $M = 4.85$, $SD = 3.31$; $t(67) = 2.14$, $p = .036$. In addition, although disparaging humor and the nonhumorous

Figure 1. Stereotyping according to type of message condition.

disparaging text presented the same stereotypes (revelers, party-oriented, and having a devil-may-care attitude), students perceived to a greater extent that these characteristics corresponded to real features of undergraduates in nonhumorous disparaging text condition ($M = 6.74$, $SD = 2.14$) than in the disparaging humor condition, $M = 4.74$, $SD = 2.01$; $t(67) = 4.01$, $p < .001$.

Also, a negative correlation between the frequency of stereotypes and the average evaluation was found $r(102) = -.40$, $p < .001$, which suggests that a more frequent use of stereotypes to describe the ingroup was associated with a less negative evaluation of the characteristics attributed to the ingroup.

Stereotyping. To test if message type can affect the stereotypic vision of the ingroup, a one-way ANOVA was conducted considering the type of message (disparaging humor, neutral humor, and disparaging text) as the independent variable and stereotyping as the dependent variable. An effect of the type of message was found $F(2, 98) = 8.08$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2 = 0.14$, confirming Hypothesis 1a (see Figure 1).

The numbers of stereotypes used to describe the ingroup was significantly higher for participants exposed to disparaging humor ($M = 1.12$, $SD = 0.91$) than in the disparagement text ($M = 0.43$, $SD = 0.55$) or neutral humor ($M = 0.65$, $SD = 0.65$) conditions.² Post hoc Sidak analyses confirm both these differences as $p < .001$.

Average evaluation. Another one-way ANOVA was conducted considering the type of message as the independent variable and average evaluation as the dependent variable. This analysis showed no effect of type of message on the average evaluation, $F < 1$, *ns*, disconfirming Hypothesis 1b.

Discussion

Our results showed that the exposure to ingroup-targeted disparaging humor facilitates, to a greater extent, the acceptance of the stereotypical characteristics presented in jokes. Therefore, it promotes more frequent negative descriptions of the ingroup. This was not a mere effect of priming negative characteristics presented to the students, rather, it was a reaction to the humorous presentation of the stimulus.

However, we did not find an effect of our manipulation on the average evaluation of the ingroup. This could be because participants first wrote stereotypic characteristics as a result of humor exposure, but then realized that they had to evaluate these characteristics that described their ingroup as well. According to cognitive dissonance theory (Festinger, 1957), one possible explanation is that participants may have changed their perception of the characteristics making them more positive to reduce cognitive dissonance associated with evaluating negative characteristics of the ingroup.

In line with previous studies on humorous communication (Ford & Ferguson, 2004), this study shows how humor releases the expression of stereotypical content, in comparison with nonhumorous disparaging text or neutral humor. Its novelty is that it has showed this effect can be found even when the target of disparaging humor is the ingroup.

Study 2

Several studies have shown the importance of analyzing group identification when examining

humor effects (LaFrance & Woodzicka, 1998; Romero-Sánchez et al., 2010). Individuals might react differently to ingroup's disparagement humor as a function of their social identification given that a higher identification leads to a greater willingness to protect the group's image (Matera et al., 2005) and to a greater group self-affirmation (Spears et al., 2004). Conversely, low identifiers may try to distance themselves from the group (Ellemers et al., 1993) and will not invest as many cognitive resources as high identifiers to maintain a positive group image (Coull et al., 2001). Considering this, a second study was proposed to explore the role of ingroup identification in the effects of exposure to disparaging humor. We aimed to replicate Study 1 findings and to test whether ingroup identification can moderate the effect of disparaging humor. In short, in this study we expected that ingroup stereotyping would be higher in the disparaging humor condition than in the neutral humor condition (Hypothesis 1), and that the degree of ingroup identification would moderate this effect of humor on the frequency of stereotypes used to describe the ingroup. For low identifiers, disparagement humor would increase ingroup stereotyping more than neutral humor; for high identifiers, the type of humor manipulation would not have an effect (Hypothesis 2).

Method

Participants and design. One hundred and sixty-seven undergraduate students (93 female and 74 male) participated in this study. Students were aged between 18 and 29 ($M = 21.67$, $SD = 2.59$). The study had a two-level independent variable and two dependent variables. The two conditions tested were disparaging and neutral humor.

Materials and measures. The same jokes as in Study 1 were used (five neutral and five disparaging). Participants were asked to indicate the degree of funniness and aversiveness of each joke. The funniness mean scores for neutral humor yielded a Cronbach's alpha of .72, and of .80 for disparaging humor.

Stereotyping and evaluation. The measures for the dependent variables were the same as used in Study 1. The main difference with Study 1 was that in Study 2, as part of the cover story to reduce suspicion of research purposes, we asked participants to write down and evaluate typical characteristics of other two groups besides students. These groups were clerical concierge and professors. The order of evaluation of the groups was counterbalanced.

Ingroup identification. Degree of identification with university students (ingroup) was measured using an 11-point scale (0 = *I do not identify at all*, 10 = *I identify completely*). This measure was presented after the jokes, at the end of the booklet.

Other variables. Age, gender, and career were registered. Also, for disparaging humor, the degree of disparagement was measured using a 5-point scale (0 = *not at all*, 4 = *very much*).

Procedure. The procedure was the same as that used in Study 1.

Results

Preliminary analysis. As expected, jokes in the disparaging humor condition were considered more denigrating than those in the neutral condition, $M = 3.66$, $SD = 1.72$; $M = 1.80$, $SD = 1.47$; $t(165) = 7.44$; $p < .001$. Also, a negative correlation was found between the ratings of funniness and aversiveness in the disparaging humor condition $r(85) = -.40$, $p < .001$. This correlation was not observed in the neutral humor condition $r(82) = -.19$, $p = .086$.³

There were no statistically significant differences between the scores of funniness for disparaging humor, $M = 1.68$, $SD = 0.88$, and neutral humor, $M = 1.58$, $SD = 0.90$; $t(165) = 0.72$, $p = .475$. However,

statistically significant differences between aversiveness scores in disparaging and neutral humor were found ($M = 1.48, SD = 1.20; M = 0.71, SD = 0.98$, respectively); $t(165) = 4.52, p < .001$.⁴ Additionally, we examined whether humor type influenced identification with the ingroup. Analysis showed it did not ($M_{\text{disparaging}} = 5.07, SD = 1.50; M_{\text{neutral}} = 4.71, SD = 1.65$), $F(1, 165) = 2.22, p = .139$.

Table 1. Results from a regression analysis examining the moderation of the effect of type of humor on stereotyping by identification with the ingroup in Study 2.

		Stereotyping				
		Coeff.	SE	<i>t</i>	95% CI	
Intercept	i_1	.59	0.05	10.77	0.48	0.70
Type of humor (X')	b_1	.39**	0.11	3.55	0.17	0.01
Identif (M')	b_2	-.05	0.03	-1.46	-0.12	0.01
Type of Humor \times Identif ($X'M'$)	b_3	-.14*	0.07	-2.12	-0.28	-0.01
		$R^2 = .09$				
		$F(1, 166) = 5.92, p < .001$				

Note. Identif: Identification with ingroup.

** $p = .005$. * $p = .035$.

Main analyses. In line with Study 1, we ran an independent t test considering humor type as independent variable and stereotyping of students as dependent variable. Results showed that in the disparaging humor condition ($M = 0.76$, $SD = 0.81$), participants used more stereotypes to describe students than in the neutral humor condition, $M = 0.39$, $SD = 0.60$; $t(165) = 3.37$, $p < .001$. Again, we did not find an effect of humor on average evaluation $t < 1.5$, *ns*.

Moderation. To understand if the degree of identification with the ingroup (I) moderates the relation between type of humor (X) and stereotyping (Y), a moderation model was tested using the macro PROCESS for SPSS developed by Hayes (2013). As presented in Table 1, the results showed an effect of disparaging humor on stereotyping for low identifiers but not for high identifiers.

Disparagement humor only predicted a higher frequency of stereotypes used to describe the ingroup when identification with the ingroup was low, $b = 0.63$ (.18), $t(166) = 3.44$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [0.26, 0.98], but not when it was high, $b = 0.16$ (.14), $t(166) = 1.15$, $p = .252$, 95% CI [-0.11, 0.43]. In this sense, Hypothesis 2 was confirmed: identification with the ingroup moderated the effect of type of humor on the frequency of stereotypes used to describe the ingroup.

Discussion

The results of Study 2 replicated the findings of Study 1, that is, disparaging humor has an effect on ingroup's stereotyping (Hypothesis 1). Again, no effects were found for average evaluation. Consistently with Study 1's results, the measure that was used may have provoked cognitive dissonance (Festinger, 1957), resulting in participants changing their evaluations after they had written students' stereotypic characteristics. Further studies should use measures that could remedy this situation.

More importantly, in this study we found that ingroup identification moderates the effect of humor on stereotyping (Hypothesis 2). In this sense, lower identification with the ingroup will promote greater stereotypic accessibility and communication. As other studies have reported, we found that ingroup identification leads to changes in humor appreciation and modifies its effects (Kochersberger et al., 2014). Individuals with low ingroup identification are more willing to accept ingroup stereotypes when presented in humorous ways, whereas for high identifiers, humor does not have this effect.

Study 3

As we previously indicated, humor's source, especially whether it comes from the ingroup or not, is an important factor in how people react to it. In this study, we manipulated jokes' source to analyze if its effects are similar to those of group identification. Rouhana (1996) showed that female participants were more offended by sexist jokes when the jokes were told by a man than when they were told by a woman, and Ford (2000, Study 3) also showed that jokes' source affected the way participants responded to sexist humor. When women or someone of unknown gender delivered the jokes, participants high in hostile sexism expressed greater tolerance to the sexist content than other participants. Thus, in this study we examined whether the fact that jokes are told by ingroup or outgroup members could have an effect on ingroup's stereotyping. As in Studies 1 and 2, we predicted the same main effect of type of humor (Hypothesis 1), and the same interaction effect of type of humor and social identification (Hypothesis 2) on stereotyping. We also expected an interaction effect between jokes' source and type of humor; that is, when the source is the ingroup, the effects of type of humor on stereotyping will be stronger than when source is the outgroup (Hypothesis 3). Considering that in our previous studies disparaging humor influenced stereotyping but not average evaluation, in Study 3 we introduced a different measure of evaluation: emotions toward the group. This measure of emotions toward the group has been shown to be a reliable, valid measure of social attitudes (Alwin, 1997; Kinder & Drake, 2009). We explored whether the way in which ingroup evaluation was measured caused the null effects found in Studies 1 and 2.

Moreover, we also explored whether manipulation could influence ingroup's perceptions of warmth and competence (Cuddy, Fiske, & Glick, 2008; Fiske, Cuddy, Glick, & Xu, 2002). These are the most important dimensions in social perception, and competence should be central in university students' ingroup identity.

Method

Participants and design. One hundred and fifty-three undergraduate students (106 female, 49 male) participated in this study. Students were aged between 18 and 30 years ($M = 21.33$, $SD = 3.11$). The design in this study was a 2 (humor: disparaging humor vs. neutral humor) \times 2 (source: ingroup member vs. outgroup member) ANOVA.

Materials and measures. The same jokes as in Study 2 were used (five neutral and five disparaging). The funniness mean scores for neutral humor yielded a Cronbach's alpha of .72, and of .75 for disparaging humor. Participants were asked to indicate degree of funniness and aversiveness for each joke. Stereotyping index for each group was measured considering the number of characteristics written (from zero to four). Besides group identification, we measured four dependent variables in

this study: stereotyping, feeling thermometer, competence and warmth, and stereotype score.

Ingroup identification. Ingroup identification was measured using the same scale as in Study 2. This measure was presented after the jokes, at the end of the booklet.

Stereotyping. Then main measure was the same as that used in Studies 1 and 2. However, in this study, besides asking participants to write down four characteristics of students and their respective evaluation, following Esses and Zanna's (1995) original procedure, we asked them to assess the prevalence of the characteristics listed within the group (in terms of percentages). From this measure, we obtained the two dependent variables described next:

Stereotyping. Refers only to the number of stereotypes written by participants to characterize the ingroup. The values ranged from 0 to 4.

Stereotype score. To have a measure that relates stereotypes, evaluation, and prevalence of those characteristics, we created a stereotyping score for each participant as done by Esses and Zanna (1995), that is, by multiplying the value of the characteristics by the percentage, and then dividing this number by the number of stereotypic characteristics written by participants.

Emotions toward the group. A feeling thermometer was used as an attitude measure (Alwin, 1997). Participants expressed the way they felt about students in general using an 11-point scale (0 = *very unfavorable feelings*, 10 = *very favorable feelings*).

Competence and warmth perceptions. A scale based on the stereotype content model (Fiske et al., 2002) was used to measure warmth and competence attributes of students. Participants were asked, "Generally speaking, to what degree do you think students have the following characteristics?" [Eight characteristics that referred to warmth and competence were presented]. Respondents answered using a 9-point scale (1 = *not at all*, 9 = *very much*). Only one factor was consistent ($\alpha = .66$), due to its content (sloth, disorganization, irresponsibility) we called it "low competence."⁵

Other variables. Age, gender, and career were registered. Also, the degree of disparagement of the jokes used was measured using a 5-point scale (0 = *not at all*, 4 = *very much*).

Procedure. We manipulated jokes' source by making salient who shared them. The booklets contained five jokes (disparaging vs. neutral) meant to be shared by a student in a group conversation arguing that they portrayed the typical student of "our university." In one condition, participants learned that the jokes had been shared by a student from another university doing an internship at "our university" (outgroup member), whereas in the other condition, the jokes had been shared by a student from their same university (ingroup member). In order to confirm that participants read correctly the information about jokes' source, we had a manipulation check. Participants were asked to write down who had shared the jokes in each condition. We only included participants who answered that question correctly. The seven who did not answer correctly, were not included in the sample. The procedure was the same as that used in Studies 1 and 2.

Results

Preliminary analysis. As expected, jokes in the disparaging humor condition were considered more

denigrating than those in the neutral condition, $M = 4.38$, $SD = 2.73$; $M = 1.22$, $SD = 2.01$; $t(151) = 9.22$, $p < .001$. Moreover, there were no statistically significant differences between the scores of funniness for disparaging humor ($M = 1.62$, $SD = 0.78$), and neutral humor ($M = 1.83$, $SD = 0.71$); $t(151) = 1.69$, $p = .10$. We did find statistically significant differences between aversiveness scores in the disparaging and the neutral humor conditions ($M = 1.06$, $SD = 0.86$; $M = 0.44$, $SD = 0.55$, respectively), $t(150) = 5.32$, $p < .001$.

As in Study 1, we analysed whether the manipulation impacted participants' identification. We found, again, no significant differences between the disparagement ($M_{\text{disparaging}} = 4.07$, $SD = 2.40$) and the neutral humor ($M_{\text{neutral}} = 3.64$, $SD = 1.92$) experimental conditions, $F(1,149) = 1.55$; $p = .215$.

Main analyses. In line with Study 2, a one-way ANOVA considered the type of humor and source as independent variables and stereotyping as the dependent variable. An effect of the type of humor on stereotyping was found $F(1, 151) = 86.92$; $p = .001$, $\eta^2 = 0.36$, confirming Hypothesis 1. Thereby, in the disparaging humor condition ($M = 1.68$, $SD = 0.95$), participants used more stereotypes to describe students than in the neutral humor condition, $M = 0.47$, $SD = 0.68$; $t(151) = 9.08$, $p = .001$. Results did not show a main effect of source $F < 1$, *ns*, nor an interaction effect between type of humor and source, $F < 1.3$, *ns*, so Hypothesis 3 was not confirmed.

We then conducted three different one-way ANOVAs examining the effects of type of humor and source on three independent variables: stereotype score, emotions toward the group, and low competence. We did not find any main or interaction effects in these three analyses, $F_s < 1$, *ns*.

Moderation. To test Hypothesis 2, the same moderation model used in Study 2 was tested. As it is shown in Table 2, results yielded an interaction effect of disparaging humor on stereotyping by identification, supporting Hypothesis 2. The effect was stronger for those who identified less with the ingroup, $b = 1.53$ (.17), $t(149) = 8.67$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [1.18, 1.88] than for those who identified more with the ingroup, $b = 0.60$ (.19), $t(149) = 3.27$, $p < .001$, 95% CI [0.24, 0.98].

Table 2. Results from a regression analysis examining the moderation of the effect of type of humor on stereotyping by identification with the ingroup in Study 3.

		Stereotyping				95% CI	
		Coeff.	SE	<i>t</i>			
Intercept	i_1	0.96	0.06	15.06	0.83	1.09	
Type of humor (X')	b_1	1.07*	0.13	8.38	0.82	1.32	
Identif (M')	b_2	-0.08	0.03	-2.84	-0.14	-0.02	
Type of Humor \times Identif ($X'M'$)	b_3	-0.20**	0.06	-3.59	-0.31	-0.09	
		$R^2 = .43$					
		$F(1, 149) = 40.79, p < .001$					

Note. Identif: Identification with ingroup.

* $p < .001$. ** $p = .005$.

Table 3. Results from a regression analysis examining the moderation of the effect of type of humor on emotions toward the group by identification with the ingroup.

		Thermometer				95% CI	
		Coeff.	SE	<i>T</i>			
Intercept	i_1	7.05	0.13	53.11	6.79	7.31	
Type of humor (X')	b_1	.25*	0.27	0.96	-0.27	0.78	
Identif (M')	b_2	.22	0.06	3.75	0.10	0.33	
Type of humor \times Identif ($X'M'$)	b_3	-.37**	0.12	-3.18	-0.60	-0.14	
		$R^2 = .15$					
		$F(1, 149) = 8.86, p < .001$					

Note. Identif: Identification with ingroup.

* $p = .34$. ** $p < .001$.

In addition, a moderation analysis was run using the emotions toward the group measure as the dependent variable. Moderation effects of identification were found again (see Table 3). The effect was significant for low identifiers, $b = 1.11$ (.37), $t(149) = 3.00, p = .003, 95\% \text{ CI } [0.38, 1.83]$, but not for high identifiers, $b = -0.60$ (.39), $t(149) = -1.55, p = .124, 95\% \text{ CI } [-1.36, 0.17]$. Also, a moderation analysis was run using the stereotype score as the dependent variable. No moderation effects of identification were found $b = 4.09$ (.52), $t(88) = 0.62, p = .532, 95\% \text{ CI } [-8.87, 17.06]$. Then, we ran the same moderation analysis using low competence as the dependent variable. No interaction effects were found $b = -0.02$ (.11), $t(149) = -0.21, p = .83, 95\% \text{ CI } [-0.25, 0.21]$. Finally, we tested a three-way interaction using PROCESS for SPSS developed by Hayes (2013, Model 3). The model was oriented to analyze whether the Type of Humor \times Identification effect on stereotyping varies as a function of the jokes' source (Hypothesis 3). The three-way interaction effect was not significant, $b = -0.01$ (.11), $t(145) = -0.13, p = .90, 95\% \text{ CI } [-0.24, 0.21]$, thereby Hypothesis 3 was not supported.

Discussion

In this study we found that the direct effect of humor on stereotyping was replicated, as participants who heard disparaging humor used more stereotypes to describe their ingroup (Hypothesis 1). Also, we replicated the moderation effect in Study 2, that is, disparagement humor influenced low identifiers, but not high identifiers (Hypothesis 2).

Even though we expected the source of the jokes to have an impact on humor effects, Hypothesis 3 was not supported. To check this, we ran another study with a different source manipulation: in one condition, jokes were attributed to a university student and in the other, to a professor. Still, no significant effects of jokes' source were observed.⁶

One of the possible reasons for these null effects is that, when the ingroup is "students from our university," it is hard to establish a relevant outgroup. In Study 3 we considered "students from another university" as the out- group, but participants could have recategorized both groups in a single common ingroup of "students" (see Gaertner & Dovidio, 2000). This could explain why in Study 3, the joke source had no main or interaction effect on stereotyping.

Also, in the study in which university professors were used as the outgroup (Endnote 6), it is possible that because some of the disparaging jokes portrayed a professor disparaging students, manipulating the source of the jokes did not have any additional impact in the reception of humor: the jokes created an intergroup relation between professors and students in both disparaging humor experimental conditions (when the source was another student or a professor).

This could be why we did not find a main or interactive effect of this type of source manipulation.

Additionally, besides the stereotyping measure used in Studies 1 and 2, in Study 3 other measures were analyzed to explore humor effects. No significant effects were observed on the measure of competence or on the measure of stereotyping. However, we did find an interaction effect of humor on the emotions toward the group measure by identification. Disparaging humor more greatly affected participants with low identification, promoting more ingroup stereotyping and also more negative attitudes toward the ingroup. This measure, in contrast with the average mean evaluation used in Studies 1 and 2 or the stereo- type score used in this study, was able to more subtly capture ingroup negative attitudes. It is possible that for participants it was easier to establish a more independent position on this item of emotions toward the group, rather than trying to conceal a characteristic and its evaluation and percentage (as was done with the stereo- type score).

General Discussion

Three studies showed that ingroup-targeted disparagement humor can influence ingroup's evaluation. This result was not due to a priming effect, because in Study 1, a nonhumorous disparaging text control condition showed no results in influencing the ingroup's evaluation. This result high- lights the effects of the "just joking" mindset that humor communication promotes, and may have implications regarding how groups are socially evaluated. It can be said that exposure to disparaging humor acts as a releaser that allows disinhibiting explicit responses in the evaluation of one's own group. These results are consistent with other humor studies based on prejudiced norm theory (Ford et al., 2008; Ford & Ferguson, 2004). According to this theory, disparaging humor creates less critical information processing and establishes an implied standard that facilitates discrimination and negative evaluation of the group members through humor.

Another important issue is that, in Studies 2 and 3, the effect of type of humor on stereotyping was moderated by ingroup identification. According to research by Matera et al. (2005), the degree of identification affects the way in which stereotypes are perceived. Low identifiers tend to use fewer cognitive resources to analyze information (Coull et al., 2001). In this case, lower identification facilitated a more relaxed reception of the humorous information, which led to perceiving and preserving a stereotypic vision of the ingroup. Also, as a consequence of threatened social identity, low identifiers may distance them- selves from the group (Ellemers et al., 1993),

resulting in more willingness to accept negative stereotypes of the ingroup. More research is needed to address these topics.

Regarding our dependent variables, in the three studies, our manipulation affected the frequency of stereotypes used to describe the ingroup, but it did not affect the ingroup average evaluation. This could be due to the way average ingroup evaluation was measured. Group members wanted to preserve a good ingroup image, but the effects of humor had already facilitated the acceptance of a stereotyped vision of students. When another type of measure was used (feeling thermometer), effects on ingroup evaluation were found. However, the fact that disparaging humor leads to a greater acceptance of the ingroup's stereotype, shows disparaging humor's great power.

This study also sheds light on the importance of social identification on humor appreciation. As mentioned before, the few studies investigating this in an ingroup context have been done in sexist humor research (Kochersberger et al., 2014; Romero-Sánchez et al., 2010). Our study moves to another ingroup context, similarly finding these interaction effects of ingroup identification on the effects of humor. This line of research focuses on humor's recipients, showing that the way they relate and identify with their ingroup will mediate humorous communication. We also tested the idea that ingroup disparaging humor source (ingroup vs. outgroup) will moderate the effects of disparaging humor on stereotyping. However, results did not support our hypothesis. Further research should use more relevant and threatening outgroups (e.g., politicians planning to apply budget cuts on education; successful entrepreneurs who did not receive a formal education).

Which mechanisms might explain the effects of disparaging humor toward the ingroup? The prejudice norm theory explains how, in an inter-group context, humor could release prejudice against the targeted group. However, in the specific case of ingroup disparaging humor, the underlying mechanism may be different. Prejudice norm theory suggests that humor releases the expression of existing prejudice; however, in the case of ingroup disparaging humor, it is possible that humor generates prejudice. Humor can serve as a means to establish local social norms (LaFrance & Woodzicka, 1998) and social norms per se could generate prejudice (Stangor, Sechrist, & Jost, 2001). Thus, when exposing students to stereotypes in a humorous way, a norm about how students should be seen is created, and participants tend to accept the stereotypes because of the influence of normative processes. Future research needs to explore whether perceived acceptance of the stereotype by others (the percentage of students that agree with the stereotype content) mediates the effects of disparaging humor on stereotyping.

Our experiments have a number of limitations that raise questions for future research. First, our experiments were limited to the expression of stereotypes toward the ingroup. Future research could explore what specific consequences stereotyping has on ingroup members' performance (such as memory tasks, intergroup contact, and the black sheep effect). Second, regarding humorous stimuli, we conducted a pilot study to obtain the jokes and then converted them into disparaging text to enable comparisons. However, we agree that we cannot rule out that difference in mode of presentation: jokes versus text—rather than difference in content—could account for some of the effects on the dependent variable (e.g., jokes are more attention-grabbing than text). Even though we tried to control for this, future research should address this issue more directly. Third, even though the scores for funniness were similar to those in other disparaging humor studies (e.g., Kochersberger et al., 2014; Romero-Sánchez et al., 2010), there were still low ratings because of the nature of this type of humor. One challenge to address in future research will be to find funnier materials to be tested throughout conditions and compare the effects of humor depending on the degree of elicited funniness.

In conclusion, the present studies show that disparagement humor influences ingroup stereotyping. Given that stereotypes, independently of their positive or negative content, serve to maintain hierarchical status relations between groups (Dovidio, Hewstone, Glick, & Esses, 2010), our results highlight the importance of analyzing how humor is used, not only when we joke about other groups, but also when we joke about ourselves.

Funding

The author(s) disclosed receipt of the following financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article: This research was supported by FPU 2011 Plan propio de Investigación UGR Grant awarded to Catalina Argüello and HUM289 Junta de Andalucía Grant awarded to Miguel Moya.

Notes

1. All jokes were originally in Spanish so their English translation may not have the same sense or any sense at all. The complete list of materials can be found in Appendix A in the online supplementary materials (jokes) and Appendix B in the online supplementary materials (text).
2. In all the studies, no significant differences by sex or age were found in any of the analyses.
3. As in Study 1, we also found a negative correlation between frequency of stereotypes used and average evaluation of students, $r(167) = -.50; p < .001$.
4. As in past studies, we found a negative correlation between stereotyping and average evaluation of students, $r(153) = -.28; p < .001$.
5. We applied principal components factor analysis and subsequent varimax rotation of participants' responses to the eight questions ($KMO = 0.56$; Bartlett's sphericity test: $\chi^2 = 135.27, df = 28, p < .001$). Three differentiated factors emerged. Factor 1 corresponded to low competence (eigenvalue of 1.85) and contained items related to disorganization and vagrancy (sloth). Factor 2 represented high warmth (eigenvalue of 1.59) related to sociability and warmth. And Factor 3 represented low warmth (eigenvalue of 1.29) with items of shyness and unsociability. A reliability analysis showed an alpha of .18 for the factor high warmth clustering three elements, and an alpha of .11 for the low-warmth factor also clustering three elements.
6. In a different study, we also manipulated joke's source. In one condition it was said that a university student delivered the jokes, whereas in the other condition, a university professor did. Thus, in this study we had a 2 (type of humor: neutral vs. disparagement) \times 2 (source: professor vs. student) ANOVA design ($n = 151$). Then we measured stereotyping as in Study 3. We replicated the results in Study 3: although a main effect of type of humor was found, indicating that disparaging humor ($M = 1.13, SD = 0.85$) led to more reported stereotypes than neutral humor did ($M = 0.73, SD = 0.74$), $F(1, 149) = 9.45; p = .003$, we did not find a significant interaction effect of humor and jokes' source on stereotyping $F(1, 147) = 0.38; p = .540$.

References

- Abrams, J. R., & Bippus, A. (2011). An intergroup investigation of disparaging humor. *Journal of Language and Social Psychology, 30*, 193–201. doi:10.1177/0261927X10397162
- Alwin, D. F. (1997). Feeling thermometers versus 7-point scales: Which are better? *Sociological Methods and Research, 25*, 318–340. doi:10.1177/0049124197025003003
- Argüello, C., Willis, G. B., & Carretero-Dios, H. (2012). The effects of social power and disparagement humor on the evaluations of subordinates. *Revista de Psicología Social, 27*, 323–336. doi:10.1174/021347412802845504
- Carretero-Dios, H., Pérez, C., & Buela-Casal, G. (2010). Assessing the appreciation of the content and structure of humor: Construction of a new scale. *Humor: International Journal of Humor Research, 23*, 307–325. doi:10.1515/humr.2010.014
- Coull, A., Yzerbyt, V. Y., Castano, E., Paladino, M.-P., & Leemans, V. (2001). Protecting the ingroup: Motivated allocation of cognitive resources in the presence of threatening ingroup members. *Group Processes & Intergroup Relations, 4*, 327–339. doi:10.1177/1368430201004004003
- Crandall, C. S., & Eshleman, A. (2003). A justification-suppression of the expression and experience of prejudice. *Psychological Bulletin, 129*, 414–446. doi:10.1037/0033-2909.129.3.414
- Cuddy, A. J. C., Fiske, S. T., & Glick, P. (2008). Warmth and competence as universal dimensions of social perception: The stereotype content model and the BIAS map. *Advances in Experimental Social Psychology, 40*,

- 61–149. doi:10.1016/S0065-2601(07)00002-0
- Dovidio, J. F., Hewstone, M., Glick, P., & Esses, V. M. (2010). *The SAGE handbook of prejudice, stereotyping and discrimination*. London, UK: SAGE.
- Ellemers, N., Wilke, H., & van Knippenberg, A. (1993). Effects of the legitimacy of low group or individual status on individual and collective status-enhancement strategies. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology, 64*, 766–778. doi:10.1037/0022-3514.64.5.766
- Esses, V. M., & Zanna, M. P. (1995). Mood and the expression of ethnic stereotypes. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology, 69*, 1052–1068. doi:10.1037/0022-3514.69.6.1052
- Ferguson, M. A., & Ford, T. E. (2008). Disparagement humor: A theoretical and empirical review of psychoanalytic, superiority, and social identity theories. *Humor: International Journal of Humor Research, 21*, 283–312. doi:10.1515/HUMOR.2008.014
- Festinger, L. (1957). *A theory of cognitive dissonance*. Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press.
- Fiske, S. T., Cuddy, A. J. C., Glick, P., & Xu, J. (2002). A model of (often mixed) stereotype content: Competence and warmth respectively follow from perceived status and competition. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology, 82*, 878–902. doi:10.1037/0022-3514.82.6.878
- Ford, T. E. (1997). Effects of stereotypical television portrayals of African-Americans on person perception. *Social Psychology Quarterly, 6*, 266–278. doi:10.2307/2787086
- Ford, T. E. (2000). Effects of sexist humor on tolerance of sexist events. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin, 26*, 1094–1107. doi:10.1177/01461672002611006
- Ford, T. E., Boxer, C. F., Armstrong, J., & Edel, J. R. (2008). More than “just a joke”: The prejudice-releasing function of sexist humor. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin, 34*, 159–170. doi:10.1177/0146167207310022
- Ford, T. E., & Ferguson, M. A. (2004). Social consequences of disparagement humor. *Personality and Social Psychology Review, 8*, 79–94. doi:10.1207/s15327957pspr0801
- Ford, T. E., Richardson, K., & Petit, W. E. (2015). Disparagement humor and prejudice: Contemporary theory and research. *Humor: International Journal of Humor Research, 28*, 171–186. doi:10.1515/humor-2015-0017
- Ford, T. E., Wentzel, E. R., & Lorion, J. (2001). Effects of exposure to sexist humor on perceptions of normative tolerance of sexism. *European Journal of Social Psychology, 31*, 677–691. doi:10.1002/ejsp.56
- Ford, T. E., Woodzicka, J. A., Triplett, S. R., Kochersberger, A. O., & Holden, C. J. (2013). Not all groups are equal: Differential vulnerability of social groups to the prejudice-releasing effects of disparagement humor. *Group Processes & Intergroup Relations, 17*, 178–199. doi:10.1177/1368430213502558
- Hayes, A. F. (2013). *Introduction to mediation, moderation, and conditional process analysis*. New York, NY: The Guilford Press.
- Kinder, D. R., & Drake, K. W. (2009). Myrdal’s prediction. *Political Psychology, 30*, 539–568. doi:10.1111/j.1467-9221.2009.00714.x
- Kochersberger, A. O., Ford, T. E., Woodzicka, J. A., Romero-Sanchez, M., & Carretero-Dios, H. (2014). The role of identification with women as a determinant of amusement with sexist humor. *Humor: International Journal of Humor Research, 27*, 441–460. doi:10.1515/humor-2014-0071
- LaFrance, M., & Woodzicka, J. A. (1998). No laughing matter: Women’s verbal and nonverbal reactions to sexist humor. In J. K. Swin & C. Stangor (Eds.), *Prejudice, the target’s perspective* (pp. 61–80). San Diego, CA: Academic Press.
- Maio, G. R., Olson, J. M., & Bush, J. E. (1997). Telling jokes that disparage social groups: Effects on the joke teller’s stereotypes. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology, 27*, 1986–2000. doi:10.1111/j.1559-1816.1997.tb01636.x
- Matera, C., Giannini, M., Blanco, A., & Smith, P. B. (2005). Autostereotyping and national identity in the Spanish context. *Interamerican Journal of Psychology, 39*, 83–92.
- McAuliffe, B. J., Jetten, J., Hornsey, M. J., & Hogg, M. A. (2003). Individualist and collectivist norms: When it’s OK to go your own way. *European Journal of Social Psychology, 33*, 57–70. doi:10.1002/ejsp.129
- McGraw, A. P., & Warren, C. (2010). Benign violations: Making immoral behavior funny. *Psychological Science, 21*, 1141–1149. doi:10.1177/0956797610376073
- Postmes, T., Spears, R., & Lea, M. (2000). The formation of group norms in computer-mediated communication. *Human Communication Research, 26*, 341–371. doi:10.1111/j.1468-2958.2000.tb00761.x
- Puertas, S. (2003). Activación automática de los estereotipos asociados al poder y su medición implícita

- (Unpublished doctoral thesis). Universidad de Granada, Spain.
- Romero-Sánchez, M., Durán, M., Carretero-Dios, H., Megías, J. L., & Moya, M. (2010). Exposure to sexist humor and rape proclivity: The moderator effect of aversiveness ratings. *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*, *25*, 2339–2350. doi:10.1177/0886260509354884
- Rouhana, N. N. (1996). *Perceiving the meta-message of disparaging intergroup jokes: The role of the joke teller's group membership and attitudes*. Unpublished manuscript.
- Spears, R., Scheepers, D., Jetten, J., Doosje, B., Ellemers, N., & Postmes, T. (2004). Entitativity, group distinctiveness, and social identity: Getting and using social structure. In I. Yzerbyt, C. M. Judd, & O. Corneille (Eds.), *The psychology of group perception: Perceived variability, entitativity, and essentialism* (pp. 293–316). New York, NY: Psychology Press.
- Stangor, C., Sechrist, G. B., & Jost, J. T. (2001). Changing racial beliefs by providing consensus information. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, *27*, 486–496. doi:10.1177/0146167201274009
- Tajfel, H., & Turner, J. C. (1979). An integrative theory of intergroup conflict. In W. G. Austin & S. Worchel (Eds.), *The social psychology of intergroup relations* (pp. 33–47). Monterey, CA: Brooks-Cole.
- Thomae, M., & Pina, A. (2015). Sexist humor and social identity: The role of sexist humor in men's in-group cohesion, sexual harassment, rape proclivity, and victim blame. *Humor: International Journal of Humor Research*, *28*, 187–204. doi:10.1515/humor-2015-0023
- Viki, G. T., Thomae, M., Cullen, A., & Fernandez, H. (2007). The effect of sexist humor and type of rape on men's self-reported rape proclivity and victim blame. *Current Research in Social Psychology*, *13*, 122–132. doi:10.1037/h0099198
- Weinstein, N., Hodgins, H. S., & Ostvik-White, E. (2011). Humor as aggression: Effects of motivation on hostility expressed in humor appreciation. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, *100*, 1043–1055. doi:10.1037/a0022495